

GENERAL PHYSICAL STRENGTH CAPABILITIES OF 13-15-YEAR-OLD JUDOKAS

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Abstract. The article is devoted to the problem of increasing the efficiency of the process of physical training of judokas aged 13-15 years. The study presents a methodology for developing speed-strength abilities of young wrestlers. The peculiarity of the methodology is that the combination of a set of general preparatory exercises performed by the method of dynamic efforts and shortened bouts carried out with maximum intensity will have a positive effect on the development of speed-strength capabilities of wrestlers aged 13 and 15 years.

Keywords: judo, wrestlers 13-15 years old, speed-strength abilities.

INTRODUCTION

Judo wrestling is an Olympic sport. Unlike other types of martial arts, judo is distinguished by the beauty and amplitude of its throws. The main task in judo wrestling is to defeat an opponent through technical actions established in the rules. To highly evaluate a technical action, a wrestler must perform a technical action over his opponents on his back while controlling it until the end of the fall. A prerequisite for a high score is the strength and speed of the technique [1].

MATERIALS AND METHODS

A judoka must have a high level of development of all physical qualities. Only with developed special dexterity can one anticipate and evade an enemy attack, as well as perform any technical actions. Without special endurance, it is impossible to actively fight throughout the entire meeting. Strength is needed to overcome the opponent's weight and active resistance when throwing [2].

A characteristic feature of competitive activity in judo is increased requirements for the manifestation of maximum efforts in the shortest possible time, as quickly as possible, so that the throw is unexpected for the opponent [1, 4].

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

It is assumed that the method of developing speed-strength abilities, combining a set of general preparatory exercises performed by the method of dynamic efforts, and shortened bouts carried out with maximum intensity, will have a positive effect on the development of speed-strength capabilities of wrestlers aged 13 and 15 years.

The main method used in the control group was the unlimited force method, and in the experimental group - the dynamic force method. Special strength training was carried out during training bouts.

During the experiment, classes were held five times a week for 1.5 hours in both groups. There was no change in training activity. The only thing that was reduced was the time of training bouts to 30

60 seconds. This time limitation facilitated the execution of a technical action by one of the parties in the shortest possible time, rather than prolonging the fight throughout the entire competition period. The judoka needed to carry out an attacking action in the period from 30 to 60 seconds of the meeting. After a successful attack, the meeting was stopped. The rest interval between meetings was 3 minutes. Number of contractions per workout - 10-15. During training fights, the opponents changed in such a way that all fights were carried out with participants in their own weight category and the partners were not repeated.

At the beginning of the study, before conducting the pedagogical experiment, we tested the speed-strength abilities of all participants in the experiment. 16 people took part in the testing, who, after testing using the paired sampling method, were divided into two groups of 8 people - control and experimental. As shown by the processing of test results before the start of the experiment, there were no significant differences between the groups in any of the testing indicators, therefore the groups are homogeneous, and it is correct to make comparisons between them (Table 1).

Table 1

Comparison of pretest results in the control and experimental groups.

Types of control tests	Control	Experimental	t	P
	$\bar{X} 1 \pm m1$	$\bar{X} 2 \pm m2$		
Standing long jump (cm)	209 ± 5,1	211 ± 5,3	0,3	> 0,05
Shot put (m, cm)	6,77 ± 0,14	6,80 ± 0,13	0,2	> 0,05
Shot throw behind the head (m, cm)	15,34 ± 0,3	15,40 ± 0,27	0,2	> 0,05

10 throws of partner's own weight through the hip (sec)	$27,6 \pm 0,5$	$28,4 \pm 0,5$	1,1	> 0,05
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Table 2

Comparison of pretest and posttest results in the experimental group.

Types of control tests	Before the experiment	After the experiment	t	P
Standing long jump (cm)	$\bar{X} 1 \pm m 1$	$\bar{X} 2 \pm m 2$		
Shot put (cm)	$211 \pm 5,3$	$227 \pm 4,3$	2,3	< 0,05
Shot throw behind the head (m, cm)	$6,80 \pm 0,13$	$7,25 \pm 0,12$	2,6	< 0,05
10 throws of partner's own weight through the hip (sec)	$15,40 \pm 0,27$	$16,30 \pm 0,24$	2,6	< 0,05
Types of control tests	$28,4 \pm 0,5$	$25,5 \pm 0,5$	4,2	< 0,01

Table 2 shows that there were positive changes in all testing indicators. The increase in the "Standing Long Jump" test was 16 cm, in the "Shot Put" test - 45 cm, in the shot throw - 90 cm and the time for performing 10 partner speed throws decreased by 3 seconds.

CONCLUSION

A distinctive feature of the exercises in this technique should be short-term completion of the task with the shortest time achievement of the result. The use of shortened exercises as part of training has a positive effect on the development of speed-strength abilities of 13-15 year old judokas. In addition to reducing the fight time for judokas, a set of general preparatory exercises was used, performed by the method of dynamic efforts, carried out with maximum intensity. Which also turned out to be effective for the development of speed-

strength abilities of judokas aged 13-15 years. This is evidenced by reliable positive changes in all testing indicators in the experimental group.

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